

Evaluating the Effects of Zeolite on the Mechanical Properties of Concrete under Various Environmental Conditions

Sajjad khonya*

1. Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences , bahcesehir university, istanbul , turkiye
Sajjadkhonya@yahoo.com

Abstract

The high cost of asphalt and the poor performance of flexible pavements in areas such as coastal regions, cargo storage areas, airplane taxiways, and roads with heavy vehicle traffic have led to the rapid development and expansion of pavements worldwide. In this study, the simultaneous addition of zeolite to cement was investigated to evaluate the mechanical properties of concrete made with cement containing these materials. Based on the compressive strength data, it was concluded that zeolite also impacts compressive strength, and the optimal amount for this condition was found to be 2.5% by weight of cement. However, it was found that no mathematical and logical relationship could be established between alkali-silica reactions and compressive strength, but adding zeolite can control the destructive alkali-silica reaction and increase compressive strength. The freeze-thaw samples showed that this pozzolan cannot be used for freeze-thaw reactions and is not suitable as an anti-freeze additive.

Key words: concrete, zeolite, compressive strength, cement

1. Introduction (Times New Roman 14pt in Bold)

Since concrete is one of the inseparable components in construction and civil engineering today, producing high-quality concrete is one of the most important needs in road construction and structural engineering. To understand the necessity of this, it should be known that no matter how carefully a structure is designed, and all the executive and computational plans are meticulously prepared, improper execution of the concrete mix design, pouring, and curing in any part of the structure can nullify all the prior design efforts. Pavement is a structure placed on the uppermost compacted layer of the existing or modified ground soil, embankments, the base of soil and rock cuts, collectively called the pavement bed. Pavement usually consists of different layers such as subbase, base, and asphalt or concrete layers, or a combination of them, each having specific technical specifications. The most critical quality factors for concrete pavement are compressive and tensile strength, with other features like stability, durability, quality, and compaction also being significant. Therefore, studies have been conducted on concrete and additives to improve these factors, addressing many concrete issues like segregation, cracking, water absorption, etc., to achieve high-quality concrete. Achieving such quality depends on various factors, the most important of which are compressive, tensile, and flexural strength. As these factors increase, the quality of concrete improves. Some new materials, like nanomaterials and pozzolans, have been able to enhance

the mechanical and physical properties of concrete significantly. These additives can transform the world of concrete at very fine levels due to their characteristics. Cement acts as the binder of aggregates in concrete and is directly related to concrete strength, while water makes the concrete workable and facilitates the hydration process. The chemical reaction between water and cement continues the hardening process, binding the aggregates into a stone-like mass.

Nanotechnology has the significant advantage of addressing weaknesses without creating issues in other concrete properties. Due to the high cost of asphalt and the poor performance of flexible pavements in areas like coastal regions, cargo storage areas, airplane taxiways, and places with heavy vehicle traffic, concrete pavements are widely developing worldwide. Since concrete pavements are used for long-term load-bearing purposes, potential failures need to be minimized by optimizing mix designs. In wet and freezing conditions, the continuous presence of water on and within the pavement, along with the use of de-icing salts, often leads to more severe damage. The freezing and thawing phenomenon is one of the main reasons for concrete pavement deterioration. Common concrete failures due to repeated freezing and thawing include random cracking, surface scaling, and joint or durability cracking. The first two types of cracking mentioned are due to insufficient air entrainment in the concrete or surface layer, and the latter phenomenon is primarily caused by low-durability aggregates. Previous studies have shown that weak tensile strength is one of the most critical problems in concrete pavements.

According to Lin and colleagues, adding up to 15% zeolite in the cement mix improves early compressive strength, and zeolite additives also shorten the hydration time. Turkish researchers conducted experiments on concrete samples containing 5, 10, 20, and 40 percent zeolite. Compressive strength was measured after 1, 2, 7, and 28 days. The results showed that after 24 hours of curing, concrete samples with zeolite additives had lower compressive strength than the control samples. The same trend was observed after 2 and 7 days. After 28 days, the compressive strength of samples containing 5% zeolite increased by 6.8% compared to the control samples. In other samples, the compressive strength increased as follows: 15.9% in samples containing 10% zeolite, 22.3% in samples containing 20% zeolite, and 4.1% in samples containing 40% zeolite.

Kanpolat and colleagues investigated concrete containing zeolite used as a mineral additive. Cement was replaced with zeolite added in 5-35%. They also tested the strength properties of concrete containing zeolite and fly ash additives. Fly ash was added at 5% of the cement weight. Compressive strength was measured after 2, 7, 28, and 90 days. According to the test results, the highest compressive strength after 28 days was achieved in samples containing 20% zeolite. For the addition of zeolite and fly ash, the optimal range was 10 to 25% zeolite and 5% fly ash.

Ahmadi and colleagues studied the effect of zeolite on the mechanical properties and durability of concrete compared to other cement additives. Experimental tests proved the good pozzolanic activity of zeolite, although zeolite reacted with portlandite differently from SiO₂ micro-particles. Additionally, researchers found that compressive strength, water absorption, oxygen permeability, chloride penetration, and electrical resistance improved in

concrete modified with different zeolite contents compared to concrete containing SiO₂ micro-particles, similar or better.

Researchers have tested zeolite additives in concrete systems. The best compressive strength results were found with a 10% increase in samples where 5% of Portland cement was replaced with zeolite. Researchers recommend using pozzolanic additives to reduce the corrosion of hardened cement paste. According to Nasrara, amorphous silicon dioxide improves corrosion resistance and increases concrete strength by reducing the porosity of the structure through the reaction with calcium hydroxide and the subsequent formation of C-S-H crystals. Following the reaction, the Ca(OH)₂ content decreases, and the C-S-H content increases, thereby providing concrete strength and durability.

Based on the research of Nagrokin and colleagues, compressive strength tests in samples containing 10% zeolite additive showed a compressive strength increase between 13.3% and 15% after 28 days. Also, replacing 10% of cement with natural zeolite increased the closed porosity and freeze resistance of concrete. The durability of samples containing up to 10% natural zeolite increased more than 3.3 times compared to the control mix.

In this study, we aim to examine the effects of adding zeolite pozzolan and find an optimal ratio of its combination to improve the mechanical properties of concrete pavement under various weather conditions.

Materials and Experimental Methodology

Zeolite

Zeolites are crystalline aluminosilicates with three-dimensional structures made from (Al)SiO₄ tetrahedra, classified based on the SiO₂ ratio. The beneficial properties of zeolites include their orderly structure, large specific surface area (approximately 600-800 m²/g), uniform pore size, and good thermal stability. Research has shown that zeolites possess molecular sieving properties, high adsorption capacity at low pressures, and minimal temperature relationship in the range of 10-150°C. Adding zeolites allows for the production of lighter structural elements without compromising strength properties. Zeolites are widely used in additives to achieve uniform surfaces and better mortar drying. Zeolite additives accelerate the cement hydration process and alter the physical and mechanical properties of cement.

Cement

In this study, Type 2 Portland cement from the Tehran Cement Plant Complex was used. Due to the sensitivity and precision required in this work, efforts were made to use a single batch of cement to maintain consistency. Additionally, environmental changes affecting the cement during different sampling processes were kept constant.

Table 1: Chemical Composition of Type 2 Portland Cement

Component	Percentage (%)
SiO ₃	1.3

Component	Percentage (%)
Al ₂ O ₃	5.0
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.0
CaO	64.04
MgO	2.0
SO ₃	2.3
C ₃ S	45.5
C ₂ S	28.0
C ₃ A	6.5
C ₄ AF	12.2

Curing Tank

In this experiment, a curing tank was used to maintain the samples, which can hold the sodium hydroxide solution and raise its temperature to 80°C (according to National Standard 8753).

Figure 1: Curing Tank in the Laboratory

Preparation of Concrete Samples

To achieve the objectives of this research and conduct compressive strength tests, several concrete samples needed to be prepared. For each mix design, three cubic samples with dimensions of 15×15×15 cm were considered for measuring compressive strength at 7 and 28 days. The pozzolans were added as powder to the aggregates and cement in the mixer. After achieving the necessary homogeneity, the mixtures were placed into cubic molds in three

layers, with each layer compacted manually using 25 strokes. The molds were demolded after 24 hours and cured in a water tank under predetermined and consistent conditions.

To assess the durability of concrete against freezing and thawing, cubic concrete samples with dimensions of 15×15×15 cm were tested according to ASTM-C666 Procedure B. The compressive strength of the samples was measured after 50 cycles of freezing at -17°C and thawing at +17°C. The reduction in strength after these cycles was considered a measure of the concrete's durability.

Figure 2: Freezer Used for Applying Freezing Conditions on Concrete Samples

A freezer, equipped with external electrical circuits, was used to apply freezing conditions to the concrete samples. This setup allowed the application of alternating freeze-thaw cycles without removing the samples from the freezer. The freeze-thaw cycles were applied according to ASTM C666 Procedure A, with both phases occurring entirely in water. Each cycle lasted approximately 8 hours: 6 hours of freezing and 2 hours of thawing. During the freezing phase, the freezer's motor was used, and a heating element was employed for rapid thawing. The cycles were controlled automatically by a timer, which switched the motor and heating element on and off as needed.

During the freezing phase, the temperature of the water and samples was maintained between -17°C and -19°C, and during the thawing phase, around +5°C. The water depth above the samples was approximately 5 mm, and the spacing between samples was 3 mm. All faces of the samples were in direct contact with water, with temperature changes occurring via water rather than the container's body. To ensure uniform conditions across all sample faces, they were placed on a 3 mm diameter wire mesh, preventing direct contact with the container.

Heater

For the samples subjected to repeated freeze-thaw cycles, the heaters shown in Figure 3 were used. After 45, 150, and 300 freeze-thaw cycles, the samples were removed from the freezer and weighed. Subsequently, they were placed in the heater for a 24-hour cycle at 100°C. After this period, the length, weight, and compressive strength of the samples were measured.

Figure 3: Heater Used in This Study

Results and Discussion

Mix Design

Row	Water (ml)	Pozzolan Powder (g)	Pozzolan Percentage	Aggregate (g)	Cement (g)
1	551	0	0%	2460	1173
2	551	29.3	2.5%	2460	1143
3	551	59	5%	2460	1114
4	551	88	7.5%	2460	1085
5	551	118	10%	2460	1055

Evaluating the Effect of Zeolite on Slump

To evaluate the impact of replacing cement with zeolite on the slump, the results from the slump test based on the percentage of zeolite replacement are shown in Figure 4.

Figure4. Effect of zeolite on Slump

As shown in Figure 4, the addition of zeolite also leads to a reduction in slump. The decrease in slump is due to the increased specific surface area of the particles. Since zeolite particles are finer than cement particles, they have a higher specific surface area. This increased surface area causes zeolite to absorb more water during mixing, resulting in a reduction in slump.

Compressive Strength

The 28-day compressive strength with different percentages of zeolite is presented in the chart shown.

Figure 5: 28-Day Compressive Strength with Different Percentages of Zeolite

28-Day Compressive Strength

28-Day Freeze-Thaw Resistance

Figure 6: 28-Day Compressive Strength under Freeze-Thaw Conditions with Different Percentages of Zeolite

Conclusion

Based on the compressive strength data, it was concluded that the addition of zeolite has a significant impact on compressive strength. With the use of 2.5% and 5% zeolite, better results were achieved compared to the control sample, with an optimal amount for compressive strength being 2.5%. In this case, a 13% increase in compressive strength was observed compared to the control sample.

Although no mathematical or logical relationship could be established between alkali-silica reactions and compressive strength, it is possible to control destructive alkali-silica reactions and enhance compressive strength by adding a certain percentage of zeolite.

Regarding freeze-thaw cycles, it was found that this pozzolan is not suitable for controlling freeze-thaw reactions, or in other words, its performance as an antifreeze agent is inadequate. The control samples and those with varying percentages of zeolite performed similarly, with no significant differences, and the performance was almost equivalent at lower percentages.

In summary, zeolite and cement combinations can be used to manage the destructive reactions in concrete effectively.

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